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ABSTRACT

Since 1972, several graph indices were introduced and studied. In this paper, we define the Banhatti degree of vertex in a graph. We propose the first and second E-Banhatti indices of a graph. A study of E-Banhatti indices in Mathematical Chemistry is a New Direction in the Theory of Graph Index in Graphs. Also we compute these newly defined E-Banhatti indices and their corresponding exponentials for wheel graphs, friendship graphs and some important nanostructures which are appeared in nanoscience.

Keywords: first and second E-Banhatti indices, first and second E-Banhatti polynomials, graph, nanostructure

1. INTRODUCTION

The simple, connected graph G is a graph with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$. The number of vertices adjacent to the vertex u called degree of u , denoted by $d(u)$. The edge e incident by the vertices u and v with edge $uv=e$. Define $d(e) = d(u) + d(v) - 2$. For other graph terminologies and notions, the readers are referred to books [1, 2].

Mathematical Chemistry is very useful in the study of Chemical Sciences. We have found many applications in Mathematical Chemistry by using graph indices, especially in QSPR/QSAR research [3].

We define the Banhatti degree of a vertex u of a graph G as

$$B(u) = \frac{d_G(e)}{n - d_G(u)},$$

where $|V(G)| = n$ and the vertex u and edge e are incident in G .

We put forward the first and second E-Banhatti indices and these are defined as

$$EB_1(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [B(u) + B(v)],$$

$$EB_2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} B(u)B(v).$$

We propose the first and second E-Banhatti polynomials as

$$EB_1(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{B(u)+B(v)},$$

$$EB_2(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{B(u)B(v)}.$$

In Mathematical Chemistry, several graph indices were put forward and studied such as the Wiener index [4, 5, 6, 7], the Zagreb indices [8, 9, 10, 11], the Revan indices [12, 13, 14, 15], the Gourava indices [16, 17, 18, 19], the Banhatti indices [20, 21, 22, 23] and the Reverse indices [24, 25].

In this paper, we establish some usefull results on the first and second E-Banhatti indices and their corresponding polynomials.

2. SOME STANDARD GRAPHS

Proposition 1. Let G be r -regular with $|V(G)|=n$ and $r \geq 2$. Then

$$(i) \quad EB_1(G) = \frac{2nr(r-1)}{n-r},$$

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(G) = \frac{2nr(r-1)^2}{(n-r)^2}.$$

Proof: Let G be r -regular with n vertices and $r \geq 2$. Then $|E(G)| = \frac{nr}{2}$. For any edge e in G , $d(e) = 2r-2$. From definition, we deduce

$$(i) \quad EB_1(G) = \frac{nr}{2} \left[\frac{2r-2}{n-r} + \frac{2r-2}{n-r} \right] = \frac{2nr(r-1)}{n-r},$$

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(G) = \frac{nr}{2} \left[\frac{2r-2}{n-r} \times \frac{2r-2}{n-r} \right] = \frac{2nr(r-1)^2}{(n-r)^2}.$$

Corollary 1.1. For a cycle C_n with $n \geq 3$ vertices,

$$(i) \quad EB_1(C_n) = \frac{4n}{n-2}.$$

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(C_n) = \frac{4n}{(n-2)^2}.$$

Corollary 1.2. For K_n with $n \geq 3$ vertices,

$$(i) \quad EB_1(K_n) = 2n(n-1)(n-2),$$

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(K_n) = 4n(n-1)(n-2)^2.$$

Proposition 2. For a path P_n with $n \geq 3$ vertices,

$$(i) \quad EB_1(P_n) = 2 \left[\frac{1}{n-1} + \frac{2}{n-2} \right] + (n-3) \left[\frac{2}{n-2} + \frac{2}{n-2} \right] = \frac{4n^2 - 10n + 4}{(n-1)(n-2)}.$$

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(P_n) = 2 \left[\frac{1}{n-1} \times \frac{2}{n-2} \right] + (n-3) \left[\frac{2}{n-2} \times \frac{2}{n-2} \right] = \frac{4n^2 - 10n + 4}{(n-1)(n-2)}.$$

Proposition 3. For $K_{m,n}$ with $1 \leq m \leq n$ and $n \geq 2$,

$$(i) \quad EB_1(K_{m,n}) = (m+n)(m+n-2),$$

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(K_{m,n}) = (m+n-2)^2.$$

Proof: Let $K_{m,n}$ be a complete bipartite graph with $|V(K_{m,n})| = m+n$ and $|E(K_{m,n})| = mn$ such that $|V_1| = m$, $|V_2| = n$, $V(K_{r,s}) = V_1 \square V_2$ for $1 \leq m \leq n$, and $n \geq 2$. Then $d(e) = m+n-2$ for any edge e in $K_{m,n}$.

$$(i) \quad EB_1(K_{m,n}) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [B(u) + B(v)] = mn \left[\frac{m+n-2}{m+n-n} + \frac{m+n-2}{m+n-m} \right] \\ = (m+n)(m+n-2).$$

$$(ii) EB_2(K_{m,n}) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} B(u)B(v) = mn \left[\frac{m+n-2}{m+n-n} \times \frac{m+n-2}{m+n-m} \right] = (m+n-2)^2.$$

Corollary 3.1. For $K_{n,n}$ with $n \geq 2$,

- (i) $EB_1(K_{n,n}) = 4n(n-1)$.
- (ii) $EB_2(K_{n,n}) = 4(n-1)^2$.

Corollary 3.2. For $K_{1,n}$ with $n \geq 2$,

- (i) $EB_1(K_{1,n}) = n^2 - 1$.
- (ii) $EB_2(K_{1,n}) = (n-1)^2$.

3. WHEEL GRAPHS

A wheel graph W_n has $|V(W_n)|=n+1$ and $|E(W_n)|= 2n$, see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Wheel graph W_n

In W_n , there are two types of edges as follows:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(W_n) \mid d(u) = d(v) = 3\}, \quad |E_1| = n.$$

$$E_2 = \{uv \in E(W_n) \mid d(u) = 3, d(v) = n\}, \quad |E_2| = n.$$

Therefore, in W_n , we obtain that $\{B(u), B(v) : uv \in E(W_n)\}$ has two Banhatti edge set partitions.

$$BE_1 = \{uv \in E(W_n) \mid B(u) = B(v) = \frac{4}{n-2}\}, \quad |BE_1| = n.$$

$$BE_2 = \{uv \in E(W_n) \mid B(u) = \frac{n+1}{n-2}, B(v) = n+1\}, \quad |BE_2| = n.$$

We calculate the first and second E-Banhatti indices of W_n as follows:

Theorem 1. Let W_n be a wheel graph. Then

$$(i) EB_1(W_n) = \frac{n^3 + 7n}{n-2}.$$

$$(ii) EB_2(W_n) = \frac{16n}{(n-2)^2} + \frac{n(n^2 + 2n + 1)}{(n-2)}.$$

Proof: From definition and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of W_n , we obtain

$$(i) \quad EB_1(W_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(W_n)} [B(u) + B(v)] = n \left(\frac{4}{n-2} + \frac{4}{n-2} \right) + n \left(\frac{n+1}{n-2} + n+1 \right)$$

By simplifying the above equation, we get the desired result.

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(W_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(W_n)} B(u)B(v) = n \left(\frac{4}{n-2} \times \frac{4}{n-2} \right) + n \left(\frac{n+1}{n-2} \times (n+1) \right)$$

By solving the above equation, we get the desired result.

By using definitions and by cardinalities of the Bhanthi edge partition of W_n , we obtain the first and second E-Banhatti polynomials of W_n .

Theorem 2. Let W_n be a wheel graph. Then

$$(i) \quad EB_1(W_n, x) = nx^{\frac{8}{n-2}} + nx^{\frac{n^2-1}{n-2}}$$

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(W_n, x) = nx^{\frac{16}{(n-2)^2}} + nx^{\frac{(n+1)^2}{n-2}}$$

4. FRIENDSHIP GRAPHS

The friendship graphs $F_n, n \geq 2$, have $2n+1$ vertices and $3n$ edges are shown in below graph.

Figure 2. Friendship graph F_4

In F_n , there are two types of edges as follows:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(F_n) \mid d(u) = d(v) = 2\}, \quad |E_1| = n.$$

$$E_2 = \{uv \in E(F_n) \mid d(u) = 2, d(v) = 2n\}, \quad |E_2| = 2n.$$

Therefore, in F_n , we obtain that $\{B(u), B(v) : uv \in E(W_n)\}$ has two Bhanthi edge set partitions.

$$BE_1 = \{uv \in E(F_n) \mid B(u) = B(v) = \frac{2}{2n-1}\}, \quad |BE_1| = n.$$

$$BE_2 = \{uv \in E(F_n) \mid B(u) = \frac{2n}{2n-1}, B(v) = 2n\}, \quad |BE_2| = 2n.$$

We calculate the first and second E-Banhatti indices of F_n as follows:

Theorem 3. Let F_n be a friendship graph. Then

$$(i) \quad EB_1(F_n) = \frac{8n^3 + 4n}{2n-1}$$

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(F_n) = \frac{4n}{(2n-1)^2} + \frac{8n^3}{(2n-1)}$$

Proof: From definition and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of F_n , we obtain

$$(i) \quad EB_1(F_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(F_n)} [B(u) + B(v)] = n \left(\frac{2}{2n-1} + \frac{2}{2n-1} \right) + 2n \left(\frac{2n}{2n-1} + 2n \right).$$

By simplifying the above equation, we obtain the desired result.

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(F_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(F_n)} B(u)B(v) = n \left(\frac{2}{2n-1} \times \frac{2}{2n-1} \right) + 2n \left(\frac{2n}{2n-1} \times 2n \right).$$

By solving the above equation, we get the desired result.

By using definitions and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of F_n , we obtain the first and second E-Banhatti polynomials of F_n .

Theorem 4. Let F_n be a friendship graph. Then

$$(i) \quad EB_1(F_n, x) = nx^{\frac{4}{2n-1}} + 2nx^{\frac{4n^2}{2n-1}}.$$

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(F_n, x) = nx^{(2n-1)^2} + 2nx^{\frac{4n^2}{2n-1}}.$$

5. H-NAPHTALENIC NANOTUBES

We consider a family of H -Naphthalenic nanotubes which is denoted by $NHPX[m, n]$, see Figure 3.

Figure 3. Graph of H -Naphthalenic nanotube

The graphs of a nanotube $NHPX[m, n]$ have $10mn$ vertices and $15mn - 2m$ edges are shown in above graph. Let $G = NHPX[m, n]$.

In G , there are two types of edges as follows:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(G) \mid d(u) = 2, d(v) = 3\}, \quad |E_1| = 8m.$$

$$E_2 = \{uv \in E(G) \mid d(u) = d(v) = 3\}, \quad |E_2| = 15mn - 10m.$$

Therefore, in $NHPX[m, n]$, we obtain that $\{B(u), B(v) : uv \in E(NHPX[m, n])\}$ has two Banhatti edge set partitions.

$$BE_1 = \{uv \in E(G) \mid B(u) = \frac{3}{10mn-2}, B(v) = \frac{3}{10mn-3}\}, \quad |BE_1| = 8m.$$

$$BE_2 = \{uv \in E(G) \mid B(u) = B(v) = \frac{4}{10mn-3}\}, \quad |BE_2| = 15mn - 10m.$$

We calculate the first and second E-Banhatti indices of *H*-Naphthalenic nanotubes as follows:

Theorem 5. Let *NHPX*[*m*, *n*] be an *H*-Naphthalenic nanotube. Then

$$(i) \quad EB_1(NHPX[m, n]) = \frac{120m(4mn-1)}{(10mn-2)(10mn-3)} + \frac{40(3mn-2m)}{(10mn-3)}$$

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(NHPX[m, n]) = \frac{72m}{(10mn-2)(10mn-3)} + \frac{80(3mn-2m)}{(10mn-3)^2}$$

Proof: From definition and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of an *H*-Naphthalenic nanotube, we obtain

$$(i) \quad EB_1(NHPX[m, n]) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [B(u) + B(v)]$$

$$= 8m \left(\frac{3}{10mn-2} + \frac{3}{10mn-3} \right) + (15mn-10m) \left(\frac{4}{10mn-3} + \frac{4}{10mn-3} \right)$$

By simplifying the above equation, we get the desired result.

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(NHPX[m, n]) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} B(u)B(v)$$

$$= 8m \left(\frac{3}{10mn-2} \times \frac{3}{10mn-3} \right) + (15mn-10m) \left(\frac{4}{10mn-3} \times \frac{4}{10mn-3} \right)$$

By solving the above equation, we get the desired result.

By using definitions and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of an *H*-Naphthalenic nanotube, we obtain the first and second E-Banhatti polynomials of an *H*-Naphthalenic nanotube.

Theorem 6. Let *NHPX*[*m*, *n*] be an *H*-Naphthalenic nanotube. Then

$$(i) \quad EB_1(NHPX[m, n], x) = 8mx^{\frac{15(4mn-1)}{(10mn-2)(10mn-3)}} + (15mn-10m)x^{\frac{8}{10mn-3}}$$

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(NHPX[m, n], x) = 8mx^{\frac{9}{(10mn-2)(10mn-3)}} + (15mn-10m)x^{\frac{16}{(10mn-3)^2}}$$

6. *HC*₅*C*₇ [*p*, *q*] NANOTUBES

We consider *HC*₅*C*₇ [*p*, *q*] nanotubes, see Figure 4.

Figure 4. 2-D lattice of *HC*₅*C*₇ [8, 4] nanotube

The graphs of a nanotube *HC*₅*C*₇ [*p*, *q*] have 4*pq* vertices and 6*pq* - *p* edges are shown in above graph. Let *G*=*HC*₅*C*₇ [*p*, *q*].

In *G*, there are two types of edges as follows:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(G) \mid d(u)=2, d(v) = 3\}, \quad |E_1| = 4p.$$

$$E_2 = \{uv \in E(G) \mid d(u)=d(v) = 3\}, \quad |E_2| = 6pq - 5p.$$

Therefore, in G , we obtain that $\{B(u), B(v): uv \square E(NHPX[m, n])\}$ has two Banhatti edge set partitions.

$$BE_1 = \{uv \square E(G) \mid B(u) = \frac{3}{4pq-2}, B(v) = \frac{3}{4pq-3}\}, \quad |BE_1| = 4p.$$

$$BE_2 = \{uv \square E(G) \mid B(u) = B(v) = \frac{4}{4pq-3}\}, \quad |BE_2| = 6pq-5p.$$

We calculate the first and second E-Banhatti indices of a nanotube $HC_5C_7[p, q]$ as follows:

Theorem 7. Let $HC_5C_7[p, q]$ be a nanotube. Then

$$(i) \quad EB_1(HC_5C_7[p, q]) = \frac{12p(8pq-5)}{(4pq-2)(4pq-3)} + \frac{8(6pq-5p)}{(4pq-3)}.$$

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(HC_5C_7[p, q]) = \frac{36p}{(4pq-2)(4pq-3)} + \frac{16(6pq-5p)}{(4pq-3)^2}.$$

Proof: From definition and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of $HC_5C_7[p, q]$, we obtain

$$(i) \quad EB_1(HC_5C_7[p, q]) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [B(u) + B(v)] \\ = 4p \left(\frac{3}{4pq-2} + \frac{3}{4pq-3} \right) + (6pq-5p) \left(\frac{4}{4pq-3} + \frac{4}{4pq-3} \right).$$

By solving the above equation, we get the desired result.

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(HC_5C_7[p, q]) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} B(u)B(v) \\ = 4p \left(\frac{3}{4pq-2} \times \frac{3}{4pq-3} \right) + (6pq-5p) \left(\frac{4}{4pq-3} \times \frac{4}{4pq-3} \right).$$

By simplifying the above equation, we get the desired result.

By using definitions and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of a $HC_5C_7[p, q]$ nanotube, we obtain the first and second E-Banhatti polynomials of a $HC_5C_7[p, q]$ nanotube.

Theorem 8. Let $HC_5C_7[p, q]$ be a nanotube. Then

$$(i) \quad EB_1(HC_5C_7[p, q], x) = 4px^{\frac{3(8pq-5)}{(4pq-2)(4pq-3)}} + (6pq-5p)x^{\frac{8}{4pq-3}}.$$

$$(ii) \quad EB_2(HC_5C_7[p, q], x) = 4px^{\frac{9}{(4pq-2)(4pq-3)}} + (6pq-5p)x^{\frac{16}{(4pq-3)^2}}.$$

5. CONCLUSION

In this study, we have defined the Banhatti degree of a vertex in a graph. We have introduced the first and second E-Banhatti indices of a graph. Furthermore, we have determined these newly defined indices for some standard graphs and certain nanotubes. This study is a new direction in Graph Indices.

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